

Computation of the Riemann Zeta Function equal to the Harmonic Series

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Abstract: The Riemann zeta function is the most important special function in the significantly large family of zeta-functions. This paper presents a theorem that related to the harmonic series and the Riemann zeta function.

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1. Introduction

In the earlier days, geometric series [1-16] with positive exponents served as a vital role in the development of differential and integral calculus and also in the summation of series involving the harmonic series and the Riemann zeta function [17, 18]. Geometric series have significant applications in physics, engineering, biology, economics, finance, management, queueing theory, computer science and medicine [19].

2. Harmonic Series and Riemann Zeta Function

The Riemann zeta function $\zeta(s)$ for all complex numbers such as $s = a + ib$ is defined by

$$\zeta(s) = 1^{-s} + 2^{-s} + 3^{-s} + 4^{-s} + 5^{-s} + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s}, \quad \forall \Re(s) > 1.$$

Where $\Re(s)$ is the real part of all complex numbers \mathbb{C} such as $s \in \mathbb{C}$.

The harmonic series is an infinite series formed by summing all positive fractions as follows:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n} = 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{5} + \dots$$

3. Computation of Riemann Zeta function for Harmonic Series

Theorem 3.1:
$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n}.$$

Proof. Let us prove this theorem using the geometric series:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) &= \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} \right) = \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{6^s} + \dots \right) \\ \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) &= \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^s} + \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{3^s} + \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{4^s} + \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{5^s} + \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{6^s} + \dots \end{aligned}$$

Simplifying this equation using the geometric series:

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) = \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^s} - 1 \right) + \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{3^s} - 1 \right) + \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{4^s} - 1 \right) + \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{5^s} - 1 \right) + \dots$$

Here, $\left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^s} - 1 \right) = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{k}} - 1 = \frac{k}{k-1} - 1 = \frac{k-k+1}{k-1} = \frac{1}{k-1}$ for $k = 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots$

Now, we conclude that

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) = 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{5} + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n}.$$

4. Conclusion

In the article, the author has proved a theorem for computation of the Riemann zeta function equal to the harmonic series. This idea can enable the scientific researchers for further involvement in research and development.

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